

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B445
Date: 05 May 2009
Take Off: 07:25:29Z
Landing: 12:28:54Z
Flight Time 5h 03m 25s

Campaign: MEVEX Dust Flight 4
Operating Area: Oman

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	Rob King	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Kindred	Met Office	
13	Filters	Anne Klaver	University of Paris	
14	LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
15	Observer 1	Said Al Sarmi	Oman Dept of Meteorology	
16	Observer 2	Humaid	Oman Dept of Meteorology	
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Dry Neph	operator does not create a log sheet
Wet Neph	No log provided
CVI	No log provided
SWS	No log provided
Mini-Lidar	No log provided

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	30 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090505_r0_b445_074227_1hz.avi
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13	Filters	Anne Klaver	University of Paris	
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FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B445
 Date: 05 May 2009
 Project: MEVEX
 Location: NE Oman

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
060840		Start-Up	0.14 kft	266	23'35.36N 58'17.66
072119	072400	Pirouette 1	0.15 kft	272	Start Hdg 270 Mag
072529		T/O	3.4 kft	086	Muscat
074227		Video	21.0 kft	123	Start Recording
074835	081052	Profile 1	21.0 - 0.32 kft	180	250ft, QNH 1009
080615		Event	3.1 kft	169	reduce descent to 500fpm
081052	082056	Run 1	0.32 - 0.31 kft	153	250ft, QNH Q1011
081333		Heimann	0.33 kft	155	Cal 25-32C
082213	082714	Run 2	0.18 - 0.19 kft	238	100'
082243		Heimann	0.21 kft	237	Cal, 25-32C
082828	090446	Run 3	0.19 - 1.6 kft	324	100-MSA, A-B
084624		Event	0.18 kft	327	Possible target
085037		Event	0.24 kft	327	Climb towards coast
085239		Event	1.6 kft	317	Level at 1.5k'
090632	093005	Profile 2	1.7 - 24.0 kft	162	
093135	093435	Run 4.1	24.0 kft	261	
093801	094011	Profile 3	24.1 - 26.0 kft	004	
094012	100010	Run 5.1	26.0 kft	003	
100528		Sonde	26.0 kft	153	Launch #01
100559	102258	Run 5.2	26.0 kft	148	
101117		Sonde	26.0 kft	153	Launch #02
101638		Sonde	26.0 kft	153	Launch #03
102238		Sonde	26.0 kft	153	Launch #04 ovhd A
102240	102855	Profile 4	25.8 - 20.1 kft	153	
102856	103855	Run 6	20.1 - 20.0 kft	013	
103856	104351	Profile 5	20.0 - 16.0 kft	334	
104351	105236	Run 7	16.0 kft	334	
105722	110834	Run 8	17.5 kft	157	Aerosol Layer
110834	111939	Profile 6	17.5 - 6.1 kft	153	
112304	113821	Run 9	6.2 - 6.1 kft	337	Aerosol Layer
113821	114343	Profile 7	6.1 - 2.4 kft	335	6-1.5k', QNH 1009
114027			4.1 kft	334	500fpm from 4k'
114343	115548	Run 10	1.6 - 1.7 kft	335	1.5k'
115709	120808	Profile 8	3.2 - 16.0 kft	338	
121442		Video	11.5 kft	338	Stop Recording
122854		Land	0.18 kft	086	Muscat, Oman
123109	123359	Pirouette 2	0.18 kft	179	Start Hdg 180 Mag
123624		Shutdown	0.19 kft	266	23'35.36N, 58'17.66E

B445 05:07:55-12:45:45

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

MEVEX – Aerosol and Land Surface Emissivity Sortie – B445**Date: 5th May 2009****Mission Scientist: Dave Pollard****T/O OOMS: 07:30Z (11:30 local)****Land OOMS: 11:45Z (15:45 local)****Location:** East coast of Oman and Ramlat Al Wahibah – Low Level Flying Area 1.

Point A: 20°30'N 59°30'E Point B: 22°00'N 58°40'E

Weather: Cloud free conditions, moderate to high aerosol loadings**Sortie Aim:** To validate forecasts of moderate aerosol conditions and the IR and microwave surface emissivity of desert surfaces coordinated with an IASI overpass.**Key Instruments:** ARIES, MARSS, SWS/SHIMS, IR Cameras, Mini Lidar, Small particulate probes, SID 3, AVAPS, Nephs, Core Chem**Sortie profile:**

Item No.	Detail	Item time	Running time	Local time
1	Perform pirouette before take off			
2	Take off OOMS		03:30:00	11:30:00
3	Transit to KAXEM at FL210	00:25:00	03:55:00	11:55:00
4	Profile descent to 100 ft at 1000 ft/min reducing to 500 ft/min in boundary layer	00:20:00	04:15:00	12:15:00
5	Fly straight and level run at 250 ft to point A	00:10:00	04:25:00	12:25:00
6	SLR at 100ft on heading of solar Azimuth	00:05:00	04:30:00	12:30:00
7	SLR at low level from A to B	00:25:00	04:55:00	12:55:00
8	Profile ascent to FL240 at 1000 ft/min to arrive at point A	00:25:00	05:20:00	13:20:00
9	2 x SLR at FL240 dropping 4 sondes during second run	00:50:00	06:10:00	14:10:00
10	Perform an orbit at bank angle to be determined by mission scientist	00:10:00	06:20:00	14:20:00
11	Profile descent to FL150 at 1000 ft/min	00:10:00	06:30:00	14:30:00
12	SLR at FL150 towards B	00:10:00	06:40:00	14:40:00
13	Profile descent to 5000 ft at 1000 ft/min	00:10:00	06:50:00	14:50:00
14	SLR at 5000 ft towards A	00:10:00	07:00:00	15:00:00
15	Profile descent to min alt at 500 ft/min towards B	00:10:00	07:10:00	15:10:00
16	SLR at min alt towards B	00:10:00	07:20:00	15:20:00
17	Recover to OOMS	00:25:00	07:45:00	15:45:00
18	Pirouette after landing			
	Total sortie time		04:15:00	04:15:00

Mission Scientist's Debrief – B445 MEVEX
5th May 2009
David Pollard

Sortie Aim:

B445 was another visit to the Ramlat al Wahibah region to characterise the atmospheric column, its dust loading and their radiative properties as well as surface emission in conjunction with an overpass of the A-Train.

Weather:

Clear skies prevailed over the operating area during the scientific phase of the sortie, as well as for the take off and transit to the operating area. On returning to Muscat, 8/8 Cs was present, with a hazy view of the sun. A pirouette was conducted despite this.

Sortie overview:

A pirouette was performed before take off. On leaving Muscat we climbed to FL210 to transit to way point KAXEM. On the initial climb, thick aerosol was evident to ~ 2000 ft before the Neph scattering dropped to ~100/m up to 8000 ft before gradually dropping to next to nothing by 10000 ft.

Profiling down from KAXEM, the top of the dust layer was, again, apparent at 10000 ft, with the Lidar showing a thicker layer at 6000 ft. At this point, Neph scattering was ~150/m and the PCASP was giving concentrations in the range 350-600/cc. The profile was interrupted to run to point A at 250 ft before dropping to 100ft. At this level the Neph scattering was the highest seen on this detachment so far (although soon to be dwarfed by Kindred's God-like sortie) at ~500/m with some spectral separation and PCASP concentrations up to 1000/cc. This was coincident with very moist conditions, the dew point depression being only about 4 C.

At this point we performed a short run (3 mins) on the solar azimuth with SWS scanning as a proxy for an orbit before turning towards point B for a longer run at min altitude. Along this run there was noticeable variation in the dust loadings reported by both PCASP and the Neph, with the Neph giving about a 30% reduction in scattering in cyclone mode. During this run the aircraft radar was showing an anomalous return at a range of about 40 NM between 1 and 3 o'clock (photo 1), which may have coincided with a surface duct feature. Depressing the radar beam seemed to reduce the return (photo 2). This was possibly because the radar was then firing under the duct or the return may have been from condensation in the turbulence probe.

At the coast, we climbed to 1500 ft and continued the run in to point B. During this run loadings remained high with some particles being counted by 2D-C!

From B we performed a profile to FL240. The top of the initial dust layer was at 10000ft with a second moist, dusty layer starting at FL160, and continuing to higher levels. At FL240 there was another short azimuth run for SWS before climbing again to FL260 in order to get above the top of the dust layer, even here there was still some Neph scattering and PCASP concentrations up to 100/cc on the run from A to B although these dropped to nothing at the northern end of the. This was followed by a second run at FL260 dropping sondes to coincide with the A-train overpass. The lidar and Mk1 eyeball revealed that the southern end of the run had significantly higher dust loadings.

This was followed by a series of short profiles and runs to sample the dust in the various layers identified. These were at: FL200, with ~100/m and 300/cc; FL160, in a clear slot; FL175, 70/m and 250/cc with some structure; 6000 ft, 150/m in the north to 200/m and

500/cc in the south and Lidar showing us in layer extending down to a clearance above the surface layer; and 3000 ft in the surface layer.
On the profile back up to transit level the top of the dust layer had risen to about 12000 ft.
Back at Muscat a pirouette was performed under 8/8 hazy Cs.

Summary:

A good sortie with interesting horizontal and vertical structure in the aerosol loadings, and hopefully a useful validation of A-train retrievals.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.445** Date **5/5/9** Name **Ponwelle** Page **1** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
07:21:32			270		Pirouette, SKC, Left
07:24:00			"		end
07:25:30					T/O
07:38	Tran	FL 185			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Profile not as well mixed as before • Thick aerosol layer to 24ft sloped top 8-10 hft or 100 m • Interesting chemistry in lowest 3hft, 2 peaks in CO K or dip in O₃
07:48:35	P1	FL 210	S	KAXEM	
					Some Neph structure in 184ft
					K in 16 hft
		104ft			Lidar: entering top of aerosol
					Neph bucks up
					then thinner layer 3km below
					followed by surface layer
		84ft			Lidar: thicker layer at 84ft
					PCASP - 350 → 600 cm ⁻¹
					Neph to 150 m ⁻¹
		124ft			Neph to 100 230 m ⁻¹

$$\frac{12}{10} \quad 34 - 195$$

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** ⁴⁶⁵ Date 3/5/19 Name P. Howard Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
8:10:52	R1	250ft			Neph ~ 330 m ⁻¹
					Moist - T 28.7°C DP 23.3°C
8:13:34					Neph ~ 350 m ⁻¹ w/ R13
					separator
8:18					Neph 500 m ⁻¹
					PCA3P 1000 cc ⁻¹
8:20:56	R1 / P2	250ft			
8:22:13	R2 / H2	100ft			SWS scan run
					Neph - 300+ m ⁻¹
8:28:28	R3	100ft	320	NA A	Neph
8:30					possibly seeing dust on radar - photo 1
					Dean depressed 5° photo 2
					could be condensat ⁿ on Turb probe
					Wet Neph - 30% redact ⁿ
					in cyclone mode
8:42:					70% inc in PCA3P
					Neph lagging behind alt
					on back down again
8:46:					Turb
8:50:57					Clings at coast
		1500ft			Sig
09:00					Pls on 210-C
09:06:42	R3	"			Level

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B. 445** Date 5/5/9 Name P. Wood Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:00:32	P2	1500ft	160		Start
		104ft			Top of dust ~ 1000ft too
					Depth actually dropped off
					between 7.5 & 10 left
		164ft			moist layer w/ peat in depth
					Quite a bit of elevated
					dust w/ peat at FL200
9:30:05	P2	FL240			
9:31:35	R4.1	"			SWS on run
9:34:35	P3				end
9:38:01	P3				Start (to get above remaining aerosol)
9:40:11	P3/R5.1	FL 200	N		Still getting some depth scatter PCASO upto 100cc ⁻¹ !
9:58					Depth now 0
10:00:10	R5.1	FL200	+	B	
10:05:51	R5.2	"	156	B	+ Sonde 1
10:11:17					Sonde 2
10:21					Lidar picking up much more at times end of run (A) Also apparent outside.
10:23:38	R5.2/P4	FL260			sonde 4
10:28:56	P4/R6	FL200			Start, Depth at ~100m ⁻¹ 300cc ⁻¹
10:38:53	R6/P5	FL200			

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** 445 Date 5/5/9 Name *P. J. ...* Page 4 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:44:00	R5/R7	FL160	330		
10:52:36	R7				End work in a clear slab going back to FL175 to sample thin layer
					PCASP steady, 250 cc ⁻¹ Filters exposing
10:57:20	R9	FL175	160		Neph ~ 70 m ⁻¹ some structure
11:08:34	R8/PC	"			
11:19:39	PC	6 hft			end, Neph scatt 150 m ⁻¹ Lidar: in solid layer down to clearance above sfc duct
11:23:04	R9	6 hft	330	A	
			330		
11:30					Jump in Neph, fall in PCASP Neph ~ 200 m ⁻¹ PCASP 500 cc ⁻¹
11:38:21	R9/P7	6 hft	330		Slow drop in Neph conc Surface layer to dew point ↑ Neph ↑ Bumper
		2.8 hft			
11:45:47	R9/R10				Neph above 100 m ⁻¹ not end
11:55:48	R10				
11:57:09	R8	3 hft			Dustier this end Coming out of orbit
		12 hft			

12:08:08 R8
 12:31:09 180
 12:38:59
 end Neph still ab ~ 30 m⁻¹
 Pirouette - horz sun 8/8 ci left
 End

B445-#mevexViRClog

```
*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 05/05/2009 09:04:03
[2009/05/05 09:04] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/05/05 09:04] <FAAM_flt_man> hillo
[2009/05/05 09:04] [FAAMOpsDetach] logged on. Operator error here as well, still using the pre-
mevex logon on my pc
[2009/05/05 09:05] <FAAM_flt_man> a lotta rust about
[2009/05/05 09:05] [FAAMOpsDetach] you at low level?
[2009/05/05 09:08] <FAAM_flt_man> just finished over desert and now climbing to FL240
[2009/05/05 09:08] <FAAM_flt_man> got the y-fronts msg
[2009/05/05 09:14] <FAAM_flt_man> are you still there?
[2009/05/05 09:15] <FAAM_flt_man> I have a message for you to relay to the ship via Seeb N Ops
[2009/05/05 09:32] <FAAM_flt_man> let me know when you get back
[2009/05/05 09:34] [FAAMOpsDetach] back here
[2009/05/05 09:37] <FAAM_flt_man> Okay, can you phone Steve Walters (no. on your local mobile) and
ask him to pass the following to HMS P...
[2009/05/05 09:38] [FAAMOpsDetach] listening...
[2009/05/05 09:44] <FAAM_flt_man> Possible target as briefed previously. Position 21 06.08N, 059
23.52E, Time 08:46:24, Hdg 210, Speed 10kts, Isolated.
[2009/05/05 09:45] <FAAM_flt_man> Ask Steve to relay it via secure Mentor no. 92973079800
[2009/05/05 09:45] <FAAM_flt_man> For attention of PWO on board HMS P...
[2009/05/05 09:45] [FAAMOpsDetach] ortland?
[2009/05/05 09:46] <FAAM_flt_man> yis
[2009/05/05 09:46] <FAAM_flt_man> shh
[2009/05/05 09:46] [FAAMOpsDetach] is that the complete msg
[2009/05/05 09:46] <FAAM_flt_man> yes, over
[2009/05/05 09:47] <FAAM_flt_man> do you copy, understand and note?
[2009/05/05 09:50] [FAAMOpsDetach] msig passed, wot's that about
[2009/05/05 09:53] <FAAM_flt_man> that's all they are saying here. It is obviously something that
has been discussed previously
[2009/05/05 09:53] <FAAM_flt_man> secret squirrel stuff
[2009/05/05 09:53] <FAAM_flt_man> you'll have to eat your phone after sending message
[2009/05/05 09:54] <FAAM_flt_man> its something we flew over...
[2009/05/05 09:56] <FAAM_flt_man> let me know when you've sent message
[2009/05/05 09:56] [FAAMOpsDetach] sent
[2009/05/05 09:57] [FAAMOpsDetach] going 4 lunch
[2009/05/05 09:58] <FAAM_flt_man> okay, mutton puffs are go
[2009/05/05 10:06] <FAAM_flt_man> 1st sonde launched, all paras okay
[2009/05/05 10:12] <FAAM_flt_man> 2n sonde launched, gps came in 40 seconds after launch
[2009/05/05 10:17] <FAAM_flt_man> 3rd sonde launched, good data from start
[2009/05/05 10:25] <FAAM_flt_man> 4th sonde launched, gps lost during aircraft turn
[2009/05/05 10:39] [FAAMOpsDetach] pizza consumed
[2009/05/05 10:41] <FAAM_flt_man> any glee to report?
[2009/05/05 11:01] <FAAM_flt_man> Have you seen Dave M today?
[2009/05/05 11:01] [FAAMOpsDetach] no glee, Membury up & about
[2009/05/05 11:02] <FAAM_flt_man> Is he okay?
[2009/05/05 11:09] <FAAM_flt_man> Also, any news from cranfill?
[2009/05/05 11:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] cannot say that I can spot any difference....
[2009/05/05 11:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] nowt from cranfill
[2009/05/05 11:11] <FAAM_flt_man> We switched back to mission net at high level when the crackling
stopped and it is still
[2009/05/05 11:11] <FAAM_flt_man> okay
[2009/05/05 11:12] <FAAM_flt_man> we are working our way down again so will see if the low level
bumping sets it awf again
[2009/05/05 11:15] <FAAM_flt_man> Did you get the config drawing sorted?
[2009/05/05 11:18] [FAAMOpsDetach] have you got an eta
[2009/05/05 11:18] <FAAM_flt_man> oh yes
[2009/05/05 11:19] [FAAMOpsDetach] are you going to tell me as well?
[2009/05/05 11:21] [FAAMOpsDetach] hiss crackle fizz
[2009/05/05 11:21] <FAAM_flt_man> turning
[2009/05/05 11:24] <FAAM_flt_man> ETA 1625L approx
[2009/05/05 11:25] <FAAM_flt_man> Please pass to ops 'n engs
[2009/05/05 11:25] <FAAM_flt_man> 3
[2009/05/05 11:25] <FAAM_flt_man> twelve
[2009/05/05 11:37] <FAAM_flt_man> have you booked a table for tonight'ssshrimp night
[2009/05/05 11:40] [FAAMOpsDetach] no, ate me pizza instead
[2009/05/05 11:41] [FAAMOpsDetach] note that the airport will be closed betwen 6 and 7 local
tonight, so you probably don't want to wait around too long after flight
[2009/05/05 11:42] <FAAM_flt_man> why is it closed?
[2009/05/05 11:42] [FAAMOpsDetach] hush hush
[2009/05/05 11:43] <FAAM_flt_man> meaning?
[2009/05/05 11:43] [FAAMOpsDetach] need to know
[2009/05/05 11:44] [FAAMOpsDetach] but there's prob a royal flight about
[2009/05/05 11:46] <FAAM_flt_man> um see, will spread the word
[2009/05/05 12:00] <FAAM_flt_man> heading back now
```

[2009/05/05 12:25] [FAAMOpsDetach] cud u make an estimate of power drawn from the a/c for science equipment without any of the large radiometers being powered?

Cloud Physics Flight Log B

Date:	Operator:	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	AUX1 Time:	AUX2 Time:
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DAU2 Disk space?

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?	y		y		y		Y		y		n	
Pre-flight checks	Vref	7.2	Ref V (~3):	2.15	Vref (>7):	N/A	El#1 V (>1):	2	Ref V:	3.2	Comms?	
	Sample flow	1.33			Flow (~1):	0.66	El#32 V (>1):	2				
	Sheath flow	17			Pressure:	1007						
					Temp (NDIT)	36.7						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
													PCASP 100-X Vref was measured yesterday and was 7.7 V
													2DC Vref was 1.2 so was cleaned to improve to 2 V
													CDP was also cleaned but no improvement in Vref. The low voltage may be because it was not allowed to warm up due to the high ambient temperatures, it improved to 3.0 after takeoff
													Left dust boundary layer at ~1 kft. Conc below 1000-2000, conc above slowly dropped from 600 to 200
07:42													Ch1 noise on pcasep 100-X
07:42:40													All heaters switched on
													Start profile 1
07:59:30	100			350		noise							
8:00:30	090			300		Noise							
8:01:30	080			350		noise							
8:02:30	070			350		Noise							
	060												
08:04:30	050			700		Noise							
	040												
	030												
08:08:00	020			400		Noise							

Cloud Physics Flight Log B

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
08:09:45	010			500		noise							
08:11:00	250 ft			900		900							Noise stopped on pcasp 100-X End of profile 1 start run 1
08:16:00													Heaters off Aerosol concentration constant
08:21:00	250ft			700		1000							End run 1
08:22:10	100 ft			700		1100							Noise on pcasp 100-X Start run 2
08:27:10	100ft			700		1100							Noise on pcasp 100-X End run 2
08:28:30	100 ft			700		1000							Noise on pcasp 100-X Start run 3
08:36:00	100 ft			600		noise							
08:41:00	100ft			1100		noise							
08:44:00	100 ft			600		noise							Spikes to 1000 and 1400 on PCASP SPP-200
08:51:00	100 ft			400		noise							End run 3
08:53:30	015			500		noise							Over land
08:56:00	015												Some images appeared on 2dc
09:04:50	015			450		noise							End run 3 Start profile 2
09:09:30	040			450		noise							
09:12:35	070			400		noise							
09:14:30	090			250		Noise							
09:16:30	110			50		noise							Passed out of aerosol layer
09:22:00	160			200		noise							
09:22:45	170			100		noise							
09:24:00													Heaters on
09:46:00	260			100		noise							
09:59:00	260			50		noise							
10:12:00	260			150		noise							
10:29:00	200			300		noise							Start run 6
10:39:00	200			200		noise							End run 6
10:44:00	160			200		noise							Dip to 100 at fl 170 Start run 7
													Horizontal structure with variations of up to 250 /cc

	Flow:	6.6	
2DC	EI#1:	1.8	Nominal
	EI#32:	1.6	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.6	Nominal – note that switching heaters on and off affects the sample flow rate the absolute concentration data for a few seconds after these events while the measurements catch up should be discarded. The exact times for these events can be determined from the flow rate parameter.
	Flow:	1.34	
CDP	Laser V:	2.6	Nominal
FFSSP	Ref V:	3.4	Nominal
SID 3	Laser V:		Not fitted
Rack Equipment			Please note SEADAS disk space remaining. 978 MB

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B445

Date:

05-05-2009

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B445-N25	----	----	Top					Blanks (FL 210)
Filters run1	B445-N26	----	----	Bottom					
Filters run 2	B445-N27	----	----	Top	08:28:55	09:05:06	R3	1296	Interruption of the sampling between 08:46:30 / 08:50:22 and 08:51:00 / 08:52:05
Filters run 2	B445-N28	----	----	Bottom	08:28:55	09:05:06	R3	1250	
Filters run 3	B445-N29	----	----	Top	10:31:27	10:38:50		43	20000 ft
Filters run 3	B445-N30	----	----	Bottom	10:31:27	10:38:50		92	
Filters run 4	B445-N31	----	----	Top	10:58:24	11:08:31		90	17500 ft
Filters run 4	B445-N32	----	----	Bottom	10:58:24	11:08:31		84	
Filters run 5	B445-N33	----	----	Top	11:23:43	11:38:00		408	6100 ft
Filters run 5	B445-N34	----	----	Bottom	11:23:43	11:38:00		436	

Flight:

B445

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B445

Date: 05 May 2009

Instruments

Core Console fwd – the keyboard trays have lots of sharp edges and corners. Arms partly shredded!
XR5M GPS – Receiver fault bit set on HORACE status page, otherwise looks okay. Fault bit cleared after takeoff.

BBRs – Upper Pyrgeometer noisy until around 0910, then okay.

TWC – Status light flashing at low level (0815). Detector bit going to 4095. Sample temperature dropped below minimum limit around 1000Z (FL260), switched on 2nd Evap heater, then okay.

Cloud Physics

SID3 not operated

old pcasp works ok below fl180, noisy above, channel 2 & higher ok

new pcasp noise from SWS 28V ?

CVI – okay

IIR – misses chunks of data at low level. Activator program kept crashing at 1010Z so stopped recording spotter until 1149Z.

Wet Neph - okay

Dry Neph -okay

CPC – u/s – not operated

Nevzorov; failed sensor, not operated

Chemistry –

AVAPS – 4 sondes launched. No. 2 – GPS started 40 seconds after launch. No. 4 – lost GPS fairly soon after launch during aircraft turn.

MARSS – okay, except for “double bounce” problem (heat related)

SWS/SHIMS - lower shims not

ARIES – okay

Mini Lidar – okay

Filters – okay

FWVS – okay

SATCOM-H: mpds service good

GIN – serviceable

AMTG screen blanked although unit still operated

Aircraft

Very loud interference on intercom just after take-off. Lasted approx 20 seconds, may have been mobile phone.

Crackling started on Mission Net and got steadily louder until unusable. All switched to Training Net and Flt intercom. Stopped on climb to high level, then okay until 1200 on profile climb from 3kft. Not so bad or constant as before.

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 1/5/09

Flight No: B 445

Pre-Flighter: Doug Anderson

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	Operator
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevezorov	Checked and OFF	Not Run
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	n/a
14	<input type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	} Operator
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Deiced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	n/a

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	CK
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	Operator
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	n/a
28	<input type="checkbox"/>			
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevezorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
43	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		 a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
46	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		
47	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

ARIES flight log

Flight: B445 page 1 of 3

Date: 05/may/09 Operator(s): S. Roberts Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: MEVEX: Dust

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle. ↔

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
05 20	—						Power on OK on 2 nd attempt
07 25	TAKEOFF						
07 35	↑	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal
07 42 08	<u>FL 210</u>	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
08 10 45	<u>250'</u>	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
08 12 07	"	240 x 1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
08 14 14	"	120 x 1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
08 15 -	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
08 16 45	"	120 x 1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
08 17 54	"	360 x 1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
08 20 59	<u>100'</u>	cal.	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
08 22 28	"	480 x 1	N Z	0	81	41	Nadir Zenith
08 26 04	"	120 x 1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
08 27 10	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
08 28 30	<u>100'</u>	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
08 30 03	"	360 x 1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
08 32 07	"	120 x 1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
08 33 16	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
08 34 40	"	360 x 1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
08 38 04	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
08 40 -	"	360 x 1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
08 42 46	"	120 x 1	Z	0	81	43	Zenith
08 43 51	"	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal
08 45 -	"	480 x 1	Z	0	81	43	Zenith
08 47 -	"	240 x 1	N	0	81	43	Nadir
08 49 19	"	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal.
08 50 39	<u>1500'</u>	480 x 1	N	0	81	43	Nadir
08 54 39	"	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal over land. v. bumpy
08 56 03	"	360 x 1	N	0	81	43	Nadir window 37C mirror 37C
08 58 -	"	120 x 1	Z	0	81	43	Zenith
08 59 -	"	120 x 1	N	0	81	44	Nadir

Brake check over bank
 (climb to 1500' for coast crossing)
 Coast crossing at 08 51 48

ARIES flight log

Flight: 3445

page 2 of 3

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
09 01 04	15001	cal	CH	0	81	44	CHcal
09 02 27	"	360x1	N	0	81	44	Nadir Still bumpy
09 04 50	"	cal	CH	0	81	45	CHcal turning
09 31 38	FL240	Z3min	Z	0	81	41	Zenith 3 minute Ci above?
09 34 52	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CHcal
09 40 07	FL260	Z3min	Z	0	81	41	Zenith 3 minute
09 42 10	"	360x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
09 45 14	"	N3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3 minute
09 56 30	"	120x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
09 57 45	"	N3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3 min
10 02 30	"	N3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3 min + Sandes + 1951 @ 1011Z to 1023
10 28 19	FL 200 ²⁰⁰	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.
10 29 40	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
10 31 73	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
10 33 26	"	120x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
10 34 30	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.
10 35 55	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
10 38 03	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
10 39 02	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.
10 43 52	FL160	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.
10 45 14	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
10 46 16	"	240x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
10 48 26	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
10 49 47	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.
10 51 06	"	240x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
10 52 49	"	240x1	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.
10 57	FL175	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.
10 58 51	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
10 59 39	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
11 01 56	"	240x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
11 03 31	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	05/05/09	Flight	B445	log pages
Operator(s)	Rob King		Campaign	MEVEX		
Departure			Arrival			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	32°C	Ch 17	32°C	Ch18	29°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					0545
Initial target temperatures	Hot	310	Cold	315		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time		
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	Cold		
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)	
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

